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Psychiatric sequelae resulting from IL17RA blockade.

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Results

- A. Brodalumab targets the IL17 receptor subunit alpha.
- B. Four patient suicides were reported in clinical trials of brodalumab in psoriasis patients.
- C. Higher rates of depression and anxiety are described in humans with psoriasis, independent of treatment with a biologic.
- D. However, treatment with a biologic for an immune disorder is itself associated with an incompletely defined risk for psychiatric sequelae resulting from use of a biologic for an immune disease.
- E. In general, a greater risk for psychiatric abnormality or disease in psoriasis was associated with the allergic or immune component of the disease: this was evident when comparing psoriasis to malignant, non-immune conditions affecting the skin like skin cancer, and to non-psoriatic skin conditions of allergic nature.
- F. Thus, an immune-derived component activated during disease likely perturbed a CNS specific target that resulted, in a small but significant number of brodalumab-treated patients, an altered psychiatric state following IL17RA blockade.
- G. Four patients completed suicide within one year of brodalumab treatment for psoriasis.
- H. Heightened psychiatric state resulting from IL17RA inhibition was likely to require a CNS-specific molecule for emergence of a psychiatric phenotype severe enough to result in suicide, albeit in a small number of patients.
- I. We posited this was a brain-derived, neurotransmitter-based or neurotrophic factor, controlled by IL17 cytokine signaling, whose expression change was the most proximal cause of multiple completed suicides.
- J. We undertook a discovery approach to identify CNS-derived factor(s) perturbed by IL17RA blockade, measuring total transcription in humans with an allergic skin disease treated with brodalumab.
 1. GSE189266
- K. We identified neuroglin-1 (*NRG1*) as a candidate CNS-derived molecule that functioned as the mediator by which IL-17 receptor blockade exerted enough influence on psychiatric state to result in four completed suicides during its clinical study.
- L. At 18 weeks, *NRG1* was the single most differentially expressed gene in the skin of patients with Hidretena suppretiva.
- M. *NRG1* was nearly silenced by brodalumab IL17RA blockade in humans with allergic skin disease.
- N. *Nrg1* has described functions in the CNS in regulation of behavior, mood, in fear extinction and in long-term potentiation (memory). A role for *Nrg1* in synaptic plasticity was also reported.
- O. A recently study that utilized genome wide association to identify single nucleotide variants conferring risk for suicide identified a separate neureglin family gene, Neureglin-3 (*NRG3*) as a risk factor for completed suicide, together suggesting a specific function for neureglins in protection against suicidal behavior or in regulation of CNS activity that supported completion of a suicide.
- P. We sought to further describe the range of candidate factors that might contribute to risk of suicide as an adverse event in brodalumab-treated patients, an IL17 receptor antagonizing antibody.
 1. GSE56338
 2. GSE50175
- Q. The IL-17 cytokine subunits are expressed throughout the organ systems, but the toleragenic properties of the IL17 cytokine family are best described in the T-cell lineage that is defined by IL-17 expression, Th17 cells.

- 1 R. Understanding how IL-17 exposure shaped the transcriptome of cells outside of the hematopoietic
2 compartment was important for discovery of a IL17/IL17RA-regulated gene, most likely derived
3 from the CNS itself, requiring measurement of the IL-17 regulated transcriptome in human cells
4 that were not Th17 cells, and non-immune services.
- 5 S. We identified IL-17 cytokine regulated gene products by measuring total transcription with
6 RNA-sequencing in lung fibroblasts following stimulation with IL-17 and TNF-alpha.
- 7 T. Two neuronal-derived genes were silenced by IL17 in human lung fibroblasts. These molecules
8 were encoded by the genes *NTM* and *NTF3*: neurotrimmin and neurotrophin-3, respectively.
- 9 U. The major neurotrophic factor that controls mood and depressive state in humans, brain-derived
10 neurotrophic factor (*BDNF*), was a significant target of IL-17 control in human lung fibroblasts, and
11 was up-regulated by exposure to IL-17. We did not, or were not able to, detect significant BDNF
12 perturbation following clinical IL17RA blockade in humans with an allergic skin disease.
- 13 V. Discovery of IL-17 regulated gene products in a non-hematopoietic cell type thus facilitated
14 identification of brain-derived or CNS-tropic molecules this cytokine could influence in the brain of
15 brodalumab-treated patients.
- 16 W. We identified here using several transcriptomic approaches candidate IL17-regulated gene
17 products that functioned to mediate suicidal behavior in humans treated with a monoclonal
18 antibody that inhibites the alpha subunit of the IL-17 receptor, IL17RA (brodalumab):
- 19 1. Neureglin-3 encoded by *NRG3*,
 - 20 2. Neurexin-1 encoded by *NRXN1*,
 - 21 3. Neurotrimmin encoded by *NTM*,
 - 22 4. Neurotrophin-3 encoded by *NTF3*, and
 - 23 5. the brain derived neurotrophic factor, *BDNF*.
- 24 X. We identified a mechanism for potentiation of suicidal behavior in a small subset of patients treated
25 with an IL17RA blockade agent which involved a collection of CNS-derived genes that were each
26 specific targets of IL-17 control outside of the hematopoietic compartment.
- 27 1. For a select number of these CNS-specific, IL-17 regulated genes identified as candidate
28 targets that exerted an observed suicidogenic effect following IL17 receptor antagonism in
clinical study of brodalumab for psoriasis, control of the candidate gene following
brodalumab administration could be observed: *NRG1* was the leading candidate identified
in this approach.
- Y. Each of these genes identified here is described to confer risk for suicide in humans, to confer risk
for psychiatric disease (e.g., schizophrenia) in humans, or has described, basic functions in the
CNS: in memory, long-term potentiation, fear extinction (anxiety), and mood (depression).
- Z. We provided evidence here, through study of the skin in humans before and after treatment with
brodalumab, through study of the Th17 lineage cell, and through study of IL-17 stimulated gene
products in non-hematopoietic cells, that together indicates a likely mechanism of action for
elevated suicide risk in humans treated with the IL17RA antagonizing antibody, brodalumab.
- AA. Psychiatric disturbances or irregularities in patients with autoimmune diseases, and the risk for
psychiatric sequelae arising from use of a biologic for treatment of an autoimmune disease requires
further study for description that provides sufficient evidence to completely account for
hematopoietic and somatic-derived factors that influence or control mood and behavior in the CNS
in humans, to support enhanced control of psychiatric state in humans with chronic disease of
autoimmune type.

Citations

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